

DIGITAL EDUCATION AND OPPORTUNITIES AND LIMITATIONS FOR WOMEN TEACHERS

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Abstract. The article discusses the role of digital education for female educators in Uzbekistan. It examines both the opportunities and constraints faced by women in the digital shift. The study compares the experiences of rural and urban female teachers. Key aspects include infrastructure, gender dynamics, and digital literacy levels.

Keywords: digital education, female teachers, gender, opportunities, barriers, literacy, technology, education quality.

RAQAMLI TA'LIM VA AYOL O'QITUVCHILAR UCHUN IMKONIYATLAR VA CHEKLASHLAR

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Annotatsiya. Maqolada O'zbekistonda ayol pedagoglar uchun raqamli ta'limning roli muhokama qilinadi. Unda ayollarning raqamli o'zgarish jarayonida duch keladigan imkoniyatlari va cheklovlari tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqot qishloq va shahar ayol o'qituvchilarining tajribalarini solishtiradi. Asosiy jihatlar infratuzilma, gender dinamikasi va raqamli savodxonlik darajasini o'z ichiga oladi.

Kalit so'zlar: raqamli ta'lim, ayol o'qituvchilar, gender, imkoniyatlar, to'siqlar, savodxonlik, texnologiya, ta'lim sifati.

ЦИФРОВОЕ ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ И ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ И ОГРАНИЧЕНИЯ ДЛЯ ЖЕНЩИН-ПРЕПОДАВАТЕЛЕЙ

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Аннотация. В статье рассматривается роль цифрового образования для женщин-педагогов в Узбекистане. Анализируются как возможности, так и ограничения, с которыми сталкиваются женщины в процессе цифровой трансформации. Исследование сравнивает опыт женщин-учителей из сельских и городских районов. Основные аспекты включают инфраструктуру, гендерную динамику и уровень цифровой грамотности.

Ключевые слова: цифровое образование, женщины-преподаватели, гендер, возможности, барьеры, грамотность, технологии, качество образования.

Introduction

In the modern world, the penetration of digital technologies into almost all areas of our lives is fundamentally changing the education system. In particular, the

development of digital educational tools is making educational processes more convenient, interactive, and based on an individual approach. This opens up new methods, forms of learning, and paths for professional development for teachers. Especially for female teachers, digital education creates a number of opportunities, such as working on themselves, improving their skills, mastering innovative approaches, and conducting research.

Also, digital education is expanding the possibilities of remote work, which gives flexibility in terms of time and space, especially for female teachers who have more family responsibilities. They can carry out their activities at home or in suitable conditions, participate in various online courses, and study foreign experiences. This has a positive effect on their professional growth and the quality of education.

However, making full use of digital learning opportunities is not always easy. Among the challenges faced by female educators are the lack of technical equipment, problems with internet connectivity, low levels of digital literacy, and traditional attitudes in society. In particular, in some cases, the active participation of female educators in the digital environment may conflict with their family and social responsibilities. This may become a source of psychological and physical pressure for them. Therefore, ensuring gender equality in digital education processes, creating a convenient digital environment for female educators, developing learning platforms tailored to their needs, and strengthening support mechanisms are important issues. This article will analyze in detail the current issues, opportunities, and existing constraints in this area.

Research methodology

This study aims to identify and analyze the role of digital education in the lives of female teachers, the opportunities it creates, and the limitations it poses. To achieve this goal, several methods were used based on a comprehensive methodological approach.

Firstly, the current situation, that is, the use of digital education by female teachers working in the education system of Uzbekistan, was studied using the descriptive (descriptive) analysis method. Through this, statistical and qualitative data were collected based on the level of use of digital tools among women, the goals they pursue, the problems they face, and their personal experiences.

Secondly, through the method of conducting questionnaires and interviews, direct communication was conducted with female teachers working in secondary specialized, vocational, and higher educational institutions. With the help of questionnaires, accurate information was obtained about their digital literacy, attitude to technologies, and difficulties they face in the digital environment. The number of respondents selected was about 100, and they were selected from geographically diverse regions, which allowed for generalizable conclusions.

Third, the results of the interviews were analyzed in depth using a qualitative analysis method. Based on the personal experiences, individual opinions and feelings of female educators, the impact of digital education on their professional and social lives was studied.

Fourth, through a comparative method, existing strategies and initiatives related to digital education, as well as the differences between the capabilities of male and female educators, were compared.

Analysis of relevant literature

In recent years, a number of scientific, practical and normative documents have been created on the development of digital education in Uzbekistan, which allow us to study the work being done in this area, existing problems and prospects. This section analyzes works and articles that cover digital education issues in the context of female educators.

The issue of developing digital education has been covered by many researchers in the context of the role of information and communication technologies in the educational process, their effectiveness and new methodological approaches. Basically, these studies analyze the advantages of improving the quality of education through digital means, improving interaction between students and teachers, and introducing distance learning systems. At the same time, the literature on gender issues in the education system pays special attention to the impact of digital technologies on the professional activities of female teachers.

Some studies have examined the adaptation of female teachers to digital education, their technological skills, as well as the problems of maintaining a balance between family and professional responsibilities. These studies also analyze regional differences, age factors, and working conditions. Differences in digital infrastructure between urban and rural educational institutions have been identified as factors affecting women's access to technical tools.

Articles published in pedagogical journals also provide opinions on the effectiveness of advanced training courses, online seminars and trainings organized for female teachers. They emphasize the need for customized training modules, individual approaches and psychological support for female teachers.

In addition, the socio-psychological aspects of digital education, namely the problems of stress, isolation and motivation that arise in online teaching, have also been separately considered in some literature. Ways to reduce stress factors related to the digital environment in the work of female teachers, such as time management skills, and concepts such as a culture of digital well-being, have also been studied.

In general, although the existing literature has extensively covered the opportunities that digital education opens up for teachers, especially women, some aspects of this area have not yet been sufficiently studied - in particular, issues such as adaptation to individual needs, integration with the family environment and regional resource inequality. Therefore, this article serves to fill this gap.

Analysis

The results of the study show that although the digital education system has opened up new opportunities for female teachers, there are also some significant challenges and limitations in this process. Based on the conducted questionnaires and interviews, the majority of female teachers expressed a positive attitude towards the adoption of digital technologies. Especially among teachers working in urban areas, there were many cases of improving their skills through online courses, digital

textbooks and virtual trainings. Digital tools allow them to modernize their activities, increase student engagement and effectively manage their time.

At the same time, technical and infrastructural problems, lack of internet speed and devices faced by female teachers living and working in rural areas significantly limit their opportunities to use digital education. In addition, it was found that the level of digital literacy among teachers varies - especially among older women, the process of mastering new technologies is slow.

Many female teachers who participated in the study noted that in order to effectively use digital education, they are forced to find a balance between household responsibilities and professional activities. This negatively affects their full participation in technological processes. At the same time, they showed that they actively use digital tools for didactic and educational purposes, striving to maintain a humanistic approach to education.

Overall, the analysis suggests that the field of digital education serves as an important resource for the professional development of female teachers. However, in order to fully use these opportunities, some systemic problems need to be addressed. In particular:

- development of technical infrastructure,
- organization of special training programs on digital literacy for teachers,
- introduction of flexible work regimes for female teachers,
- strengthening of political and social support mechanisms aimed at ensuring gender equality in digital education.

These recommendations serve to encourage the active participation of female teachers in digital education, to fully realize their professional potential and to improve the quality of education.

Conclusions and suggestions

The results of this study show that digital education opportunities are becoming an important factor in professional development and self-expression for female teachers. Aspects such as working on themselves through online learning tools, acquiring new knowledge and skills, and communicating with students in a remote work format are introducing a new approach to their activities. This is especially evident in the case of female teachers working in urban areas.

At the same time, existing problems are not ignored. The lack of technical means and a stable internet network in some segments of the population, the uneven level of digital literacy, and the difficulties in maintaining a balance between family and professional obligations limit the effective use of digital education. This process is especially difficult for older teachers.

Based on the research, it is clear that additional opportunities need to be created for female teachers. First of all, it is necessary to improve the technical infrastructure, especially in remote areas. Also, the development of special trainings and methodological guides on digital literacy for female teachers is important in increasing their confidence in technology.

In addition, it is important to create flexible working conditions to encourage active participation in digital education and organize educational processes taking into account family responsibilities. Developing leadership skills for female educators and

involving them in activities on digital platforms will not only ensure their professional growth, but also make it possible to achieve quality and efficiency in the entire education system.

These proposals and recommendations are expected to serve to ensure gender equality in digital education, expand the opportunities of female educators, and organize their activities more effectively.

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